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D4.7 University Course Design

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Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	6
LIST OF FIGURES	8
LIST OF TABLES	8
ABBREVIATIONS	9
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	10
1 INTRODUCTION	11
1.1 THE VITALISE PROJECT	11
1.2 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT	11
1.3 MASTER’S SCOPE	12
1.4 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT	12
2 METHODOLOGY FOR CURRICULUM DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT	13
2.1 COURSE CONCEPTUALIZATION AND DESIGN	13
2.2 COURSE MODULES AND SKILLS	16
2.3 TEACHING MODULES	18
3 METHODOLOGY FOR LESSONS DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT	20
3.1 THE 5E MODEL	20
4 LECTURES’ CONTENT	23
4.1 COURSE INTRODUCTION AND ORIENTATION.....	23
4.1.1 <i>Course objectives and learning outcomes</i>	23
4.1.2 <i>Holistic view and specific knowledge on sustainability</i>	24
4.1.3 <i>Platform interaction and expectation</i>	24
4.2 THEORETICAL FOUNDATION OF USER CENTRIC METHODS AND INNOVATION	25
4.2.1 <i>Living Labs methodology fundamentals</i>	25
4.2.2 <i>From user-centred design to implementation science: the journey</i>	26
4.2.3 <i>Agile development in LL and the learning loop in a complex community of LLs</i>	27
4.2.4 <i>User centric research methods and processes</i>	28
4.3 INNOVATION TYPOLOGY	28
4.3.1 <i>Radical/disruptive, incremental and social innovation</i>	28
4.3.2 <i>Data/Technology driven innovation</i>	30
4.4 STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION	30
4.4.1 <i>Stakeholder identification</i>	30
4.4.2 <i>Open Innovation Ecosystems</i>	31
4.4.3 <i>Stakeholder analysis</i>	32
4.5 NEEDS ASSESSMENT AND PROBLEM DEFINITION.....	32

D4.7 University Course design

4.5.1	<i>Needs analysis and problem identification</i>	32
4.5.2	<i>Techniques and tools for needs assessment</i>	33
4.6	SURVEY, INTERVIEW AND FOCUS GROUP METHODOLOGIES IN USER CENTRIC RESEARCH	34
4.6.1	<i>An introduction to qualitative inquiry, quantitative and mixed methods in research using a Living Lab approach</i>	34
4.6.2	<i>Practical guidelines for Survey, interview and focus group methodologies in user centric research</i>	35
4.7	CO-CREATION SESSIONS IDEATION, CONCEPTUALIZATION AND PROTOTYPING TECHNIQUES	36
4.7.1	<i>Idea, concept and prototype in implementation science</i>	36
4.7.2	<i>Co-creation and workshop facilitation techniques</i>	38
4.7.3	<i>Tools for Co-creation and Open Innovation sessions</i>	39
4.8	TESTING EXPERIMENTATION AND VALIDATION TECHNIQUES	40
4.8.1	<i>Typology of testing</i>	40
4.8.2	<i>Living Labs as Research Infrastructures</i>	41
4.9	RESEARCH ETHICS, LEGAL ISSUES, DATA MANAGEMENT AND PROTECTION	41
4.9.1	<i>Basic Ethics Concepts</i>	41
4.9.2	<i>IPR and copyright in open innovation</i>	43
4.9.3	<i>FAIR data and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)</i>	44
4.10	USER / RESEARCH PANEL MANAGEMENT	44
4.10.1	<i>User research & Panel management</i>	44
4.10.2	<i>Panel members profiling</i>	45
4.10.3	<i>Panel engagement and panel data</i>	45
4.11	LIVING LAB PROJECT PLANNING AND MANAGEMENT	46
4.11.1	<i>Research design for own "user centric project"</i>	46
4.11.2	<i>Innovation projects and activities carried out within a Living Lab</i>	46
4.12	ENTREPRENEURSHIP	47
4.12.1	<i>Transforming an idea into a sustainable business model</i>	47
4.12.2	<i>How LL services can accelerate access to the market</i>	47
4.13	SUSTAINABILITY	48
4.13.1	<i>LL Labeling framework (ENoLL Evaluation)</i>	48
4.13.2	<i>Living Lab Business Model, Business Plan and Sustainability</i>	49
4.13.3	<i>Pitfalls in open innovation towards a sustainable Living Lab ecosystem</i>	50
4.13.4	<i>Realistic Evaluation</i>	50
5	NEXT METHODOLOGICAL STEPS	52
6	CONCLUSIONS	53
7	REFERENCES	54
	APPENDICES	57
	APPENDIX 1	57

List of Figures

FIGURE 1. DYNAMIC CURRICULUM MODEL	14
FIGURE 2. COURSE DESIGN (THIRD PHASE OF THE DYNAMIC CURRICULUM MODEL)	15
FIGURE 3. WORKING SPREADSHEET WITH COURSE TEACHING MODULES AND TEACHING SKILLS PER MODULE	16
FIGURE 4 LEARNING SKILL'S ESTIMATION OF TIME REQUIRED TO BEING TAUGHT.....	17
FIGURE 5 THE SKILLS THAT WOULD REQUIRE A FULL 2-HOUR LECTURE TO BE TAUGHT	18

List of Tables

TABLE 1. COURSE MODULE NAMES AND KEY SKILLS	18
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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
KT	Knowledge Translation

Executive summary

This document reports on the preparation of the new postgraduate course that is designed and implemented in Task 4.5 Design and implementation of common postgraduate courses. The main objective of this deliverable is to present the methodology and the steps that have been followed until M18 for the design of the postgraduate course. The methodology is divided in two parts: the first part concerns the methodology followed for the design of the course, that is based on the Dynamic Curriculum model while the second part presents the 5E model which is a framework followed for the content and implementation of the master course. Finally, the document presents the first draft summaries of the lesson that will be included in the master course. These summaries are a starting point that will help to analyse further and homogenize the course material before the final piloting.

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g. healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling inperson Transnational Access to 17 Living Labs research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Purpose of the document

The objective of the WP4 -T4.5 Design and Implementation of common postgraduate courses is to support the design of university courses that will educate potential new researchers for the Living Lab value in research and innovation. This deliverable includes the guidelines and supporting material for a university postgraduate course implementation. The effort to design the graduate program began in the spring of 2022 [M12].

The methodology followed for this curriculum development is based on both discussions and exchanges between partners and online research. The overall methodology is divided in two parts, the methodology used for the design of the curriculum structure and the methodology that will be followed for the lessons design and implementation.

First, the methodology for defining the objectives of the MSc and the learning skills and competencies that students will acquire upon completion of the MSc is described. At this initial stage, the emphasis was on brainstorming to gather information from researchers and partners. To this end, brainstorming sessions were held with fellow researchers and stakeholders and informal discussions were initiated. Through these informal discussions we gathered important information. Topics raised in these discussions included, for example, the creation of an MSc course and the business models used for respective sustainable operations. This strategy was adopted to make the approach more flexible, as well as to offer a way of gathering personal thoughts and opinions on the challenges to be addressed when engaging students in the innovation process using LLs. This method also allowed us to gain valuable insights because the core group participants revealed experiences, reactions and concerns that would not be available in the literature. In addition, all

phases of the creation of the worksheets are indicated in this stage. The way of communication and interaction between the core team members is described.

Following the Design phase, presented in this deliverable, the Implementation phase will focus on the creation of the lectures based on the 5E teaching method, including engagement, exploration, explanation, elaboration and evaluation. The 5E Instructional Model brings coherence to different teaching strategies, provides connections among educational activities, and helps teachers make decisions about interactions with students (BSCS 2019). Compared to traditional teaching models, the 5E learning cycle results in greater benefits concerning students' ability for scientific inquiry (Bybee 2009). Finally, during the piloting phase of the VITALISE project a subset of the lectures will be piloted within some of the universities of the consortium.

1.3 Master's Scope

The postgraduate course focuses on innovation through Living Labs methodologies, services and entrepreneurship with the title: Master's Degree Programme "MSc in Innovation through Living Labs and Entrepreneurship". The MSc course aims to be provided outside of the official university program in the universities of the consortium (AUTH, McGill, LAUREA, UPM) in order to introduce Living Lab services and infrastructure as a methodology for innovation to young researchers and attract them to use the Living Lab framework in their work. The skeleton of the pedagogical method and the abstract of the lectures were designed in the framework of this deliverable.

1.4 Structure of the Document

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the VITALISE project, aspects related to it, and the purpose of the document.
- **Section 2** discusses the overall methodology for the development of the MSc course curriculum and also the implementation of the methodology.
- **Section 3** presents the 5E methodology that will frame the MSc lectures design and development.
- **Section 4** includes the summaries of the lessons that will be developed for the Master course.
- **Section 5** presents next steps towards the actual piloting of the Master course in the framework of VITALISE implementation.
- **Section 6** provides some concluding remarks for this deliverable.

2 Methodology for curriculum design and development

In general, curricula developed through collaborative curriculum design incorporate reformist aspirations aimed at enriching students' experiences or outcomes. Engaging in this process requires curriculum designers to reflect on their own practice, challenge their assumptions, share expertise, and negotiate meaning in relation to how to meet students' needs (Kali, McKenney, & Sagy, 2015). In the methodology section we introduce the process of designing curricula and its pivotal components needs analysis and assessment; design, development and implementation; its outcomes and relevance for students, teachers and teaching practices; and the long-term effects through continuation, sustainability and up-scaling. According to Voogt et al. (2015) and Williamson (2013), what is essential for curriculum design and sustainability is not only discourse about what needs to be taught and learned, but also (and primarily) developing an understanding of the relationship between curriculum as intention and as reality. This section presents the methodology that was followed for the conceptualization and design of the curriculum for the MSc course as well as the practical steps for its implementation.

This Master course is being developed following the guidelines and standards of ISO 9001:2015 in Software Design, Development & Production, Design & Implementation of Education/Training Programmes. This ISO standard includes compliance practices regarding the plan-do-check-act methodology and the process-oriented approach to document and review the structure, responsibilities, and procedures required to achieve effective quality design and delivery of a training. AUTH is keeping track of the records for the design as the Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation follows this procedure in every educational program that is being produced. The final documents will be included in D4.2 Online educational materials (final version).

2.1 Course Conceptualization and Design

The Dynamic Curriculum Development model (Walker, 1971; Reynolds & Skilbeck, 1976; Stenhouse, 1980; Harden, 2000) [Figure 1] was followed for the course conceptualization and Design. This model runs in parallel with the one used for the Harmonization of the Living Lab procedures (reported in D2.2 Evaluation process and tools). The two methodologies share common activities and pillars under different names in order to be inline with the state of the art methodologies in each field. This model considers the process of curriculum development as dynamic in nature. The model allows for changes to be initiated at any point in the process and thus enables a flexible design of a graduate curriculum that meets the educational needs of an ecosystem such as living labs.

Figure 1. Dynamic Curriculum Model

The **first phase** of the model starts with analysing the context in which the curriculum is developed. The analysis of the situation includes a study of the different curriculum sources (students, stakeholders and disciplines or subject matter), and careful examination of the different curriculum influences (internal, external, and organizational) that affect curriculum development. Following the selected methodology, and by involving a number of experts, professors and students, a gap in the postgraduate curricula was identified. The target group of students that the MSc aims at will consist of various disciplines (e.g. doctors, engineers, psychologists, innovation managers). The proposed course will focus on innovation through Living Labs methodologies, services and entrepreneurship.

The proposed master course is determined by the following basic characteristics

- Aims to create an innovative and pioneering postgraduate program of study which will combine the philosophy and culture developed by the LLs with the creation of innovation within a business development framework
- Aims to provide educational as well as business content
- It has specific learning and educational goals with time, financial and quality limitations
- During its implementation it will utilize human and material resources.

The result of the situation analysis led to the **second phase** which includes the development of the goals and objectives of the curriculum as well as the learning skills and competencies. In this phase the thematic areas were decided and the expected skill per area were identified. (Appendix 1).

In the **third phase**, it was decided that the approach to be followed will belong to the skills-focused category and, in addition, it should include, objectives, content and parameters that are important in a MSc course (Figure 2). The third phase involved the grouping of the expected skills that can be part of the same lecture and the initial description of the lectures.

Figure 2. Course Design (third phase of the Dynamic Curriculum model)

During each phase of the course design, the involved stakeholders provided feedback on the following questions (Thabane, et al. (2010)):

- What are we going to do?
- Why are we doing it
- How will it be done?
- Who will be involved?
- How long will it last?
- What can go wrong and how can it be fixed?
- How will the timeline and budget estimated?
- How did we make certain decisions?
- How will the success of the master course will be assessed?

Finally, to decide what the key objectives and intended competences of the trainees should be when the proposed postgraduate programme is completed, the following aspects were taken into account:

- the parameters of the programme
- the time and financial constraints
- the impact and societal needs
- the expertise of the participants

The third phase has not yet been finalized. The finalization of third phase along with the implementation of fourth and fifth phase will take place in the following months. As the Dynamic Curriculum model is an ongoing, non-linear process, the VITALISE team might reconsider and make changes to materials already defined from the first 3 phases.

2.2 Course modules and skills

A core group of experts in courses designing, innovation management and living lab methodology was formed from members of the VITALISE consortium. After concluding to the target objective of the course and the target users, the identification of the learning skills and competencies took place. A set of initial learning skills led to the creation of the teaching modules (groups of skills belonging to the same concept). To make this process more effective, “Cards-Lectures”, cards containing the learning skills and describing what each skill is, were designed and used. The usage of the cards facilitated the core group to identify the modules during an in-person meeting. Then, after discussions among the members of the core group, more learning skills were added to the corresponding teaching modules. In addition, initial ideas on hands on assignments, tools and methods for collaboration among the students and expected studying outcomes were also included. The first version of the course was composed of 13 course teaching modules and ~7 learning skills each [Figure 3].

Course module #	Course module name	Key skills to be learned	Element 1	Element 2	Element 3	Element 4	Element 5	Element 6	Element 7	STUDYING TASK	COLLABORATION AMONG STUDENTS	STUDYING OUTCOME	LITERATURE / REFERENCES
1	Course introduction and orientation	Understanding the course objectives and committing to forthcoming studying tasks	Introduction of course objectives and learning outcomes	Introduction of course participants via icebreaker exercise	Student groups formation							Students will know each other and student groups are formed	
2	Theoretical foundation of user-centric methods and innovation	Understanding the theoretical foundations and becoming familiar with the current body of knowledge regarding user-centric innovation	Introduction of the “family” of different user-centric research methods and processes (list what are covered)	Benefits and challenges of user-centric research and innovation	What is a living lab? Research infrastructure	User-centric design / Design thinking	Design print	Agile development		Reading and familiarizing collection of user-centric literature	Individual task	Automated quiz to verify theory knowledge?	
3	Innovation typology	Understanding different innovation types and their relation to user-centric innovation methods	Open innovation	Sustainable innovation	Social innovation	Radical/disruptive vs. incremental innovation	Business model innovation	Data driven innovation	Technology driven innovation	Reading and familiarizing collection of innovation literature	Individual task	Automated quiz to verify theory knowledge?	
4	Stakeholder identification	Ability to understand typology of different users in an innovation ecosystem. Ability to conduct stakeholder analysis	Understanding and classification of different user types	Quadruple helix theory	Open innovation ecosystems	Degrees of user involvement	Techniques and methods for stakeholder analysis, mapping and identification			Identify and report relevant stakeholders for the defined case(s), if possible, real-life cases otherwise carefully selected simulated cases.	Done by a small student group. Transnational peer reviewing among course participants from different countries.	Report describing relevant stakeholder for the selected case by using one or more tools presented in the course module	

Figure 3. Working spreadsheet with course teaching modules and teaching skills per module

The titles of the course teaching modules were:

- Course introduction and orientation
- Theoretical foundation of user-centric methods and innovation
- Innovation typology
- Stakeholder identification
- Research ethics and legal issues
- User/research panel management
- Data management and protection
- Survey, interview and focus group methodologies in user-centric research
- Need assessment and problem definition
- Co-creation sessions
- Ideation, conceptualization and prototyping techniques
- Testing and validation techniques
- Living lab project planning and management.

Indicative learning skills emerged in the first version were:

- Understanding the course objectives and committing to forthcoming studying tasks
- Understanding the theoretical foundations and becoming familiar with the current body of knowledge regarding user-centric innovation
- Understanding different innovation types and their relation to user-centric innovation methods
- Ability to understand typology of different users in an innovation ecosystem

- Ability to conduct stakeholder analysis
- Ability to execute living lab research in ethical way and follow GDPR requirements
- Ability recruit and manage user panels
- Ability to create data management plan and foster open data principles
- Ability to execute conduct survey, interview and focus group methods
- Ability to identify user needs, scope the problem and find the opportunity for innovation, Ability to understand and use co-creation techniques for ideating, concept creation and prototyping
- Understanding the theoretical foundations of ideas, concepts, and prototypes
- Understanding different types of testing methods
- Ability to formulate testing plan and conduct testing for different types of tests
- Ability to define project plan for a living lab project.

Then, in order to identify more learning skills, more partners from the consortium were involved. The online spreadsheet was used by the members of the consortium to revise, add comments and missing learning skills.

The next step, towards designing the lectures, was to estimate the time/effort each teaching skill would require for being taught. To do so, the Planning Poker approach was borrowed by the Scrum framework. Planning Poker is a consensus based, gamified technique to estimate the complexity and effort needed. Planning Poker depends upon input from all the experts with their different fields of expertise who are actively involved. In planning poker, members of the group make estimates by playing numbered cards face-down to the table (or online through specially designed tools, Socratic and Scrum Poker were used in our case), instead of speaking them aloud. The cards are revealed, and the estimates are then discussed. The goal of Planning Poker is not only to provide the estimation of the resources/time need but to increase communication among the members and lead to a common understanding. In our case, and given the large number of learning skills, the duration of each had to be estimated, we used the Planning Poker approach only in the beginning. Figure 4 presents the concluded duration estimation of each of the learning skills.

MSc in Innovation through Living Labs and Entrepreneurship										
Course modules	Course module name	Key skills to be learn	Element 1	Element 2	Element 3	Element 4	Element 5	Element 6	Element 7	Element 8
1	Course introduction and orientation	Understanding the course objectives and committing to forthcoming studying tasks	Introduction of course objectives and learning outcomes 10 min	Introduction of course participants via icebreaker exercise 25	Introduction of SE Method of Instruction 10	Transdisciplinary communication and understanding 60	Holistic view and specific knowledge on sustainability 45	Use of virtual learning environments and resources 30	Understand platform interaction and expectations 25	Networking with participants and experts 30
2	Theoretical foundation of user centric methods and innovation	Understanding the theoretical foundations and becoming familiar with the current body of knowledge regarding user centric innovation	Introduction of the "family" of different user centric research methods and processes (list what are covered) Research and Development (R&D) process; In-situ methods to capture the temporal and contextual nuances of users' practices; 15	Benefits and challenges of user centric research and innovation Innovation as a process of turning opportunity into new ideas and of putting these into wide used practice 10	What is a living lab? Living lab as research infrastructure Types of LL environments: Research LLs, Corporate LLs, Organizational LLs, Intermediary LLs, A time limited LLs. 60 "How LLs can become part of a transformative institutional change that draws on both top-down and bottom-up strategies in the pursuit of sustainability	User-centric design / Design thinking The meaning to know what the user actually wants and needs (D) 30	Public- Private Partnership (PPP) LLs as "functional regions" enabling actors have settled down PPP of companies, public entities, universities, institutes and individuals (2) Innovation ecosystem, co-creation 25	Agile development Learn how established LLs can adopt this approach to renew their surveys, look into problems from a different angle and redesign internal processes 30	Basic concepts theories and terminology it call this element: key concepts and terminologies in KT knowledge translation: How is it done? What are the gaps, what causes them and what are interventions. Implementation science (Separating KT from IS) Methods and theories to do KT/KM 1. A learning loop in a complex community like LL, includes Social learning - networks and forums for deliberation and exchange 90	Living Lab Key Principles: value influence sustainability openness realism 15
	Innovation typology 90 min ALL	Understanding different innovation types and their relation	Open vs closed innovation vs idea	Sustainable innovation	Social innovation inclusivity and sustainability placing citizens at the heart of the innovation process	Radical/disruptive vs. incremental innovation	Business model innovation	Data driven innovation	Technology driven innovation	Innovation as a key driver for economic and social growth

Figure 4 Learning skill's estimation of time required to being taught

Before starting this, the members were invited to select 1-2 learning skills that would require a 2-hour lecture to be taught. The commonly selected lectures were used as a reference of a lecture's

duration (The 2-hour training skills are yellow highlighted in Figure 5). Once the core team started thinking the same way, the Planning Poker was abandoned in order to save time.

Course modules	Course module name	Key skills to be learn	Element 1	Element 2	Element 3	Element 4	Element 5	Element 6	Element 7	Element 8
1	Course introduction and orientation	Understanding the course objectives and committing to forthcoming studying tasks	Introduction of course objectives and learning outcomes	Introduction of course participants via icebreaker exercise	Introduction of SE Method of Instruction	Transdisciplinary communication and understanding	Holistic view and specific knowledge on sustainability	Use of virtual learning environments and resources	Understand platform interaction and expectations	Networking with participants and experts
2	Theoretical foundation of user centric methods and innovation	Understanding the theoretical foundations and becoming familiar with the current body of knowledge regarding user centric innovation	Introduction of the "family" of different user centric research methods and processes (list what are covered) Research and Development (R&D) process; In-situ methods to capture the temporal and contextual nuances of users' practices;	Benefits and challenges of user centric research and innovation Innovation as a process of turning opportunity into new ideas and of putting these into wide used practice	What is a living lab? Living lab as research infrastructure	User-centric design / Design thinking The meaning to know what the user actually wants and needs	Design print	Agile development Learn how established LLS can adopt this approach to renew their surveys, look into problems from a different angle and redesign internal processes	Types of LL environments: Research LLS, Corporate LLS, Organizational LLS, Intermediary LLS, A time limited LLS.	Living Lab Key Principles: value influence sustainability openness realism

Figure 5 The skills that would require a full 2-hour lecture to be taught

Taking into account the estimated duration of each learning skill and the teaching module, the learning skills were group to form full 2-hour lectures. Given the short duration of some lectures, and after reflecting on the result, the core team decided to combine similar topics. The final number of lectures was reduced to 36, organized in 13 teaching modules, as shown in OAppendix 1.

The final step was to provide the description of each of the lectures. During this step, all involved partners were invited to select the lectures they had expertise/experience at and to prepare a description for each of them. To emphasize the importance of following a common pedagogical approach for all the lectures, even from the very first steps, the consortium was provided with the selected methodology to be followed. The 5E methodology (3.1), standing for engage, explore, explain, elaborate, and evaluate, was selected and communicated to the partners. This was necessary to enable appropriate guidance to be given to the participants who would write the course summaries.

2.3 Teaching modules

The final list of the Titles and Key Learning skills of the concluded teaching modules for the Master course is presented in Table 1. The lectures summaries are presented in Section 4.

Table 1. Course module names and key skills

Course module name	Key skills to be learn
Course introduction and orientation	Understanding the course objectives and committing to forthcoming studying tasks
Theoretical foundation of user centric methods and innovation	Understanding the theoretical foundations and becoming familiar with the current body of knowledge regarding user centric innovation

Innovation typology	Understanding different innovation types and their relation to user centric innovation methods
Stakeholder identification	Understanding and classification of different user types and the different contexts they operate in
Needs assessment and problem definition	Ability to identify user needs, scope the problem and find the opportunity for innovation. Understanding better the problem to be solved.
Survey, interview and focus group methodologies in user centric research	Ability to conduct survey, interview and focus group methods
Co-creation sessions Ideation, conceptualization and prototyping techniques	Ability to understand and use co-creation techniques for ideating, concept creation and prototyping. Recognise the potential of co-creation
Testing experimentation and validation techniques	Understanding different types of testing methods. Ability to formulate testing plan and conduct testing for different types of tests
Research ethics and legal issues. Data management and protection	Ability to execute living lab research in ethical way and follow GDPR and other national/international regulation requirements. Ability to create data management plan and foster open data principles
User / research panel management	Theoretical foundations of user/research panel management
Living lab project planning and management	Ability to define project plan for a living lab project
Entrepreneurship	Collaborate effectively with your team in LLs and generate ideas that drive innovation and entrepreneurship
Sustainability	How the co-creation of knowledge and practices takes place within LLs to address sustainability challenges

3 Methodology for lessons design and development

The course development methodology also includes the model that is adopted for the design of the Master course's lectures. The 5E teaching model, standing for engage, explore, explain, elaborate, and evaluate, was selected for the lectures to provide the best possible teaching for all students. In each phase of the 5E Teaching Model, teachers have the opportunity to carefully consider how the evidence collected and information obtained builds students' understanding of how to solve a problem within the ecosystem of living labs.

3.1 The 5E Model

The 5E Model is a step-by-step guide for designing meaningful instructional experiences. The effectiveness of the 5E model of instruction has been supported by research in education in recent years (Rodriguez et al., 2019; Sung and Chiu, 2021; Chan et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2022). The 5E model consists of five stages: engage, explore, explain, elaborate, and evaluate. Effective completion of the phases provides a coherent instruction to the learner for a better understanding of knowledge, attitude, and skills within an excellent progression of cognition (Garcia et al., 2021). The 'engage' phase includes activities to arouse curiosity about the new subject that students will learn based on their prior knowledge (Wilson et al., 2010). During exploration and explanation activities, students are expected to discover knowledge by using scientific process skills (Bybee et al. (2006)). These phases are very important for the understanding, application, and analysis levels of Bloom's taxonomy, although they are not separated by sharp boundaries. In the elaboration and evaluation stages, students are expected to use higher-order thinking skills because these stages are very precious for Bloom's cognitive levels of evaluating and creating (Lam et al. 2022). The following instructions and examples were created in order to drive the development of the lesson's description. More specifically, the main elements of the 5E model were introduced as:

- **Engage:** generate interest, access prior knowledge, connect to past knowledge, set parameters of the focus, frame the idea.
 - Teacher: motivates, creates interest, taps into what students know or think about the topic, raises questions and encourages responses.
 - Students: attentive in listening, ask questions, demonstrates interest in the lesson, responds to questions demonstrating their own entry point of understanding
- **Explore:** experience key concepts, discover new skills, probe, inquire, and question experiences, examine their thinking, establish relationships and understanding.
 - Teacher: acts as a facilitator, observes and listens to students as they interact, asks good inquiry-oriented questions, provides time for students to think and to reflect, encourages cooperative learning.
 - Students: conduct activities, predicts, and forms hypotheses or makes generalizations, become good listeners, share ideas and suspend judgment, record observations and/or generalizations, discuss tentative alternatives.
- **Explain:** encourages students to explain their observations and findings in their own words, provides definitions, new words, and explanations, listens and builds upon discussion from students, asks for clarification and justification, accepts all reasonable responses.
 - Teacher: connects prior knowledge and background to new discoveries, communicates new understandings, connects informal language to formal language.
 - Students: explain, listen, define, and question, use previous observations and findings, provide reasonable responses to questions, interact in a positive, supportive manner.

- **Elaborate:** apply new learning to a new or similar situation, extend and explain concept being explored, communicate new understanding with formal language.
 - Teacher: uses previously learned information as a vehicle to enhance additional learning, encourages students to apply or extend the new concepts and skills, encourages students to use terms and definitions previously acquired.
 - Students: apply new terms and definitions, use previous information to probe, ask questions, and make reasonable judgments, provide reasonable conclusions and solutions, record observations, explanations, and solutions.
- **Evaluate:** assess understanding (self, peer and teacher evaluation), demonstrate understanding of new concept by observation or open-ended response, apply within problem situation, show evidence of accomplishment.
 - Teacher: observes student behaviours as they explore and apply new concepts and skills, assesses students' knowledge and skills, encourages students to assess their own learning, asks open-ended questions.
 - Students: demonstrate an understanding or knowledge of concepts and skills, evaluates their own progress, answer open-ended questions, provide reasonable responses and explanations to events or phenomena.

The following questions, along with potential tools that could be used, were given to the partners to facilitate the description of the lectures.

- **Engage**
 - What do you think about stakeholder mapping and analysis? (Brainstorm)
 - What do you know about stakeholder matrices and stakeholder maps.? How did you learn it? (Access prior knowledge)
 - As part of the development of any communication strategy or plan, is it essential that stakeholder analysis is carried out at an early stage? (Ask questions)
 - Tools: Padlet, Google Classroom Question, Mentimeter, iClicker
- **Explore**
 - Explore how stakeholder mapping and prioritisation helps programme leaders customize their outreach and assess what will work best for their culture, context and situation
 - Watch videos, Read Articles and related papers, Listen to podcasts, Interview
 - Offline Task: Conduct field work in a local Living Lab
 - Tools: Google Scholar, YouTube, LMS Online Discussion
- **Explain**
 - Encourage students to explain their observations and findings in their own words about methods of stakeholder analysis.
 - Define criteria for identifying and prioritizing stakeholders and select engagement mechanisms.
 - Allow students to teach each other concepts by recording videos
 - Tools: Google Hangout, Zoom, FlipGrid
- **Elaborate**
 - Apply the learning to new or novel situations therefor stakeholder mapping involves the identification of the interested parties, their interests, possible impacts and influences and the ways in which they interact between themselves or within the process.
 - Tools: Quizizz, Shared Google Docs, Drawings, Spreadsheets, Kahoot!
- **Evaluate**
 - The participants engage in dialogue with competing experts and decision makers based on questions they develop in small group discussions with trained moderators.

D4.7 University Course design

- Show evidence of accomplishment stakeholder mapping
- Tools: Socrative, Google Forms

4 Lectures' content

This Section contains the summaries of the lessons selected and provided by VITALISE partners according to their experience and expertise. The current version might contain overlapping information as the lessons have not yet been edited and structured. These summaries will be further analysed and contextualized according to the 5E methodology instructions. In the next stage of the project, we will work on testing and adapting the abstracts to a common template that is in line with the 5E methodology of instruction. All the materials will use as a starting point the final outcome of the summaries in order to produce a well-structured course.

Each subsection presents a different course module. Each module consists of different lectures with specific learning skills that will be acquired and the description of the lecture content.

4.1 Course introduction and orientation

The Course introduction and orientation will introduce the students to course's objectives and committing to forthcoming studying tasks

4.1.1 Course objectives and learning outcomes

Learning skills

- Introduction of course objectives and learning outcomes
- Introduction of course participants via icebreaker exercise
- Introduction of the 5E Method of Instruction
- Transdisciplinary communication and understanding

Lecture content

The module will be divided into four main parts: the first will be dedicated to the programme objectives and learning outcomes; the second to the difference between the course participants and the importance of the icebreaker exercise; the third will focus on the methodology of the 5E teaching method and how to apply it to the postgraduate curriculum. The fourth part will focus on transdisciplinary communication and understanding.

The module will initially introduce students to the scope and usefulness of understanding innovation through LLs with practical and relevant real-life examples and data.

This lesson will focus on course objectives and learning outcomes. The learning aims and objectives will be analysed and a general description of what this postgraduate programme aims to achieve will be given. There will also be an interactive discussion on the learning outcomes and how these will describe in measurable terms what a student is able to do as a result of completing a learning experience (e.g. lesson, module or project).

Student learning outcomes will be treated as statements that define what students will know, be able to do or be able to demonstrate when they complete a course or programme of study. Learning outcomes will be analysed by lecturers and will relate to the core knowledge of LLs, innovation and entrepreneurship to be mastered or the critical skills that can be demonstrated either in an individual course or a programme of study. These outcomes will include the competences, knowledge and skills that students will demonstrate at the end of the course or programme of study.

Then, emphasis will be placed on engaging and developing creative communication among students, using specific templates and interactive tools such as Student Response Systems, Collaborative Text Editors-Readers, Diagramming, Conferencing, Conversing Text. In addition, a case study on the practical application of the 5E methodology will be presented and discussed.

To complete the lecture, students will be asked to complete an evaluation through a questionnaire developed with the online tool Socrative Student.

4.1.2 Holistic view and specific knowledge on sustainability

Learning skills

- Holistic view and specific knowledge on sustainability
- Use of virtual learning environments and resources
- Practical skills related to considering sustainability related issues of user / customer integration and orchestration through becoming acquainted with specific cases of Living

Lecture contents

The lesson will provide a holistic view on sustainability with focus on ecological, economic and social aspects of sustainability while also presenting specific cases of Living Labs in the participants' countries and worldwide, particularly in the context of sustainability.

The starting point will involve an introduction to the 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals¹ with the students also familiarizing themselves with the OECD analysis of the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development² as well as the EU policies and guidelines on sustainability³.

During the lecture the students will be introduced to their assignment which will involve individual and group work via the digital learning platform Canvas and Zoom conferencing system (incl. breakout group work). Quiz on theoretical aspects of sustainability in the context of Living Labs Blog to be published on course work (in groups) in Laurea Journal Lite

4.1.3 Platform interaction and expectation

Learning skills

- Understand platform interaction and expectation
- Networking with participants and experts

Lecture content

This course will focus on understanding the function, platform interaction and expectations and the expectations of the networking with participants and experts to be used in the online graduate program. The course will be divided into two main parts: the first will be devoted to the difference between traditional and online education and the importance of pedagogical use of digital media in

¹ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

² <https://www.oecd.org/dac/sustainable-development-goals.htm>

³ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/sustainability_en

teaching. The second half will focus on effective networking with participants and experts and how to support the learning environment by using social bookmarking, social networking, WebQuests and Video Tools.

In the following, emphasis will be placed on the importance of educational interactions that take place using traditional forms of communication, such as emails, videoconferences, instant messages, face-to-face meetings. Emphasis will be placed on explaining what the development of new forms of communication and networking, such as web-based platforms or other interactive Internet-based technologies such as videoconferencing, which have eliminated many barriers to effective communication and networking between teachers and students, especially during the covid-19 pandemic.

The second half of the course will be dedicated to the process of networking with participants as a step towards applying what was discussed in the first part of the course (understanding the interaction and expectations of the platform) and understanding how to identify the priorities that can arise in an online teaching.

Finally, the lecture will cover the topic of the advantage of the virtual environment created by e-learning and the Internet and how teachers and students can access a wide range of online resources. We will focus on how online learners learn to work in the digital age in a networked environment such as social networking sites (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn), virtual meetings, virtual learning environments, email or chat sessions. Finally, examples of online communication networks will be presented that provide platforms for teachers to interact, communicate and collaborate with other teachers or educators and can provide services that can further develop effective communication and synchronization. To complete the lecture, students will be asked to complete an evaluation through a questionnaire developed with the online tool Mentimeter.

4.2 Theoretical foundation of user centric methods and innovation

The goal of the Theoretical foundation of user centric methods and innovation is to familiarize the students with the current body of knowledge regarding user centric innovation

4.2.1 Living Labs methodology fundamentals

Learning skills

- What a living lab is.
- Living lab as research infrastructure
- Types of LL environments: Research LLs, Corporate LLs, Organizational LLs, Intermediary LLs, A time limited LLs.
- How LLs can become part of a transformative institutional change that draws on both top-down and bottom-up strategies in the pursuit of sustainability
- Living Lab Key Principles: value, influence, sustainability, openness, realism

Lecture content

This lecture aims to provide the essentials of the Living Lab methodology, including pitfalls, challenges, roles, responsibilities, operations, value creation and value chain, access to infrastructures, learn how to build a long-term multi-stakeholder commitment/partnership, and to

develop open innovation processes and partnerships. It explores the different types of the Living Lab environments, such as Research LLs, Corporate LLs, Organizational LLs, Intermediary LLs, A time limited LLs, as well as the key principles of LLs.

At the beginning of the session a short entry point quiz (multiple and closed answer) will be provided to assess the knowledge of the participants prior to the start of the lesson. The instructor will ask students some icebreaker questions about the Living Lab methodology to increase engagement and participation. The lecture will provide a full set of knowledge about the fundamentals of the LL methodology. At the end of the session, and after the Q&A session, the entry point quiz will be provided again to assess the increase of knowledge after the session.

4.2.2 From user-centred design to implementation science: the journey

Learning skills

- User-centric design and Design Thinking.
- The meaning to know what the user actually wants and needs.
- Basic concepts, theories and terminology in Knowledge Translation: How it is done. What the gaps are, what causes them and what the interventions are.

Lecture content

This lecture will focus on two main aspects, user-centred design and how these methodologies yield results to complete the journey to implementation science.

The first part of the class will focus on the basics of user-centred design (UCD) process and the Design Thinking methodology and all its existing strands, in which designers focus on the users and their needs in each phase of the design process. We will also analyse how it is used, how it is implemented, what results are expected and what it is useful for in the context of innovation. In the same way, we will explore the weaknesses, gaps and possible challenges that this type of methodologies has. Finally, we will dive into who our user is and how we can accurately target their needs and desires.

Once these facts are understood, we will move on to the second part of the lecture where we will have a space dedicated to the basic concepts of knowledge translation (KT) and how we can interpret the results generated. In this context, we will also understand how it is done, what are the most commonly used methodologies for this purpose, what are the gaps, what causes them, what are interventions, and what barriers exist. We will end the class with some insights on the last part of the journey, which is implementation science and what are the most widespread theories and methodologies in the context of innovation and living labs, we will understand how evidence-based interventions can be successfully integrated into practice, i.e., overcoming the “black box” between research and practice.

Knowledge translation is a multi-phase process that aims to promote the uptake of research evidence to bridge existing research to practice gaps, improve practices and ultimately, patient care (Straus et al., 2011; Graham et al., 2006). Implementation science is concerned with the theories, models and methods used in KT to inform and improve HPE (Bauer et al., 2015). We describe each in greater detail next.

Despite the widespread use of diverse terms to refer to KT (e.g. diffusion, research utilization, knowledge exchange) there is broad consensus that KT aims to optimise the adoption, appropriate

adaptation, delivery, and sustainability of effective practices and policies within defined contexts (Brown et al., 2017). KT originated from the biomedical and clinical sciences in response to a growing recognition that diagnostic tools and treatments were often either overused, underused or misused in many areas of health care (Schuster et al., 1998; McGlynn et al., 2003), that together, resulted in suboptimal care and poor health outcomes. Over two decades of research on the root causes of this under- over- and/or misutilization of scientific evidence in clinical practice have converged on several individual and organizational factors that alone, or in combination, influence clinician behaviour. KT is used to address these various root causes, and typically consists of three distinct phases (described in detail in section 3): a) documenting the nature and the magnitude of research-practice gaps; b) identifying and explaining the individual, organizational and system level factors (i.e. determinants) that support or inhibit the use of research findings to inform practice; and c) designing and evaluating the impact of theory-driven and tailored strategies to increase the use of research findings (Graham, 2012).

4.2.3 Agile development in LL and the learning loop in a complex community of LLs

Learning skills

- Agile development Learn how established LLs can adopt Agile development to renew their surveys. Look into problems from a different angle and redesign internal processes
- A learning loop in a complex community like LLs, including Social learning - networks and forums for deliberation and exchange

Lecture content

This course will focus on flexible development and flexible learning, how well-established LLs can adopt this approach to renew their research, consider problems from a different angle and redesign internal processes. In addition, it will consider the ability to identify an innovation ecosystem of stakeholders, the ability to define the concept of co-creation, the methodology of joint planning and, finally, how to support a learning cycle in a complex community such as LLL, which includes social learning - networks and forums for discussion and exchange.

The lesson will be covered nine dimensions: Flexibility (open to new concepts), Speed (taking quick action), Experimenting (trying new ways of doing things), Performance Risk-Taking (seeking out challenges), Interpersonal Risk-Taking (not afraid of constructive conflict), Collaborating (open to ideas from others), Information Gathering (takes the initiative to seek the information they need), Feedback Seeking (appreciates the opportunity to improve), Reflecting (thinks about how they can apply improvements to future challenges)

Finally, the lecture will cover the topic of supporting individual and community needs, providing students with the tools to design a needs assessment with the use of social learning. In particular, we will deal with the identification of social learning as one of the most effective strategies for adapting to the dynamically changing environment of LLs, the different forms of learning from others manifested in different taxonomic categories of increasing complexity, and the emotional states of others caused by interactions with the environment of LLs. To complete the lecture, students will be asked to complete an evaluation through a questionnaire developed with the online tool Socrative student, Mentimeter and Quiz Development.

4.2.4 User centric research methods and processes

Learning skills

- Foundations of Human-Computer Interaction Methodologies
- Introduction of the "family" of different user centric research methods and processes
- Research and Development (R&D) process;
- In-situ methods to capture the temporal and contextual nuances of users' practices;
- Benefits and challenges of user centric research and innovation
- Innovation as a process of turning opportunity into new ideas and of putting these into wide used practice

Lecture content

In this lesson students will gain an overview of various user centric research methods. After the course students will be able to characterize and differentiate various research methodologies and will have the necessary skills to compare, select and apply appropriate methodologies to a given problem.

Within the introduction session, students will learn to understand the design research space as a landscape based on Sanders (2008). The main dimensions of the landscape, reflected in the approach (research led versus design led) and mind-set (expert mindset versus participatory mindset) will be discussed, and various methodological approaches and corresponding methods will be debated in detail, i.e., user-centered design (e.g., contextual inquiry, usability testing), participatory design ("Scandinavian" methods), and practice-based research (applied ethnography). Beyond this, more design-led approaches such as critical design (e.g., cultural probes) or research through design / constructive design research will be covered.

Students will gain insights into the Methodological foundations (goals, characteristics, and main methodological commitments/paradigm, e.g., constructivism, interpretivism) and common methods applied in the context (basically focusing on contemporary methods). Moreover, the historical background of various approaches will be debated, and a discussion of practical examples (research papers) will help students to better understand the benefits and challenges of various approaches. To foster the collaboration within the group and the lecturer there will be two main communication channels, i.e., Discord (chat, video/voice calls in group work) and Webex for lecture parts and presentations. Moreover, interactive tools, such as Miro will be used for brainstorming, feedback and for exchanging thoughts.

4.3 Innovation typology

The Innovation typology module will aim at the understanding of the variety of the different innovation types and their relation to user centric innovation methods.

4.3.1 Radical/disruptive, incremental and social innovation

Learning skills

- Open vs closed innovation and idea

- Sustainable innovation
- Social innovation
- Inclusivity and sustainability placing citizens at the heart of the innovation process
- Radical/disruptive vs. incremental innovation

Lecture content

This lecture will focus on two innovation aspects: i) radical / disruptive and incremental innovation and ii) social innovation.

The first part of the lecture will examine the nature of radical / disruptive and incremental innovations as well as the dynamic ways in which they may affect markets. It will clarify the concept, the nature and the aim of innovation, in the domains of research and invention, and its effect in entrepreneurship. After an introduction to the fundamental concepts of innovation management at both a strategic and operational level, we will proceed with an analysis of the types and dimensions of innovation, defining the role of innovators as personas and organizations. How can we kick-start the innovation process in our organizations and what are the sources of innovation? What are the challenges of radical vs incremental innovation and their impact from a business perspective? The lecture will elaborate on modern methods, tools, and tactics used for managing the innovation process and in the design of innovation management strategies. Technology transfer practices, technology foresight techniques will be analysed.

The first part of the lecture is designed to be interactive, and its content is complemented with case studies elaborating on specific real-world cases which help in understanding the relevant concepts and approaches of the types of innovation and innovation management practices. Participants are expected to familiarize themselves with the concepts of innovation, and tools and techniques that can effectively manage it.

The second part of the lecture will focus on how end users and service producers co-create for a social innovation in order to promote innovative approaches, understanding that social inclusion is at the heart of sustainable development. Innovation is both a primary source of systemic environmental and sustainability challenges and in this module, we will focus on how to coordinate user-centric innovation environments where users and producers collaborate to create innovation within an open and trusted ecosystem that facilitates business and corporate innovation. Mechanisms will be offered to promote approaches for new inclusive and sustainable innovative models, involving socioeconomic sectors and citizens in their management.

To apply these user-centric inclusive methodologies for sustainable innovation based on the Living Lab approach, the course will be divided into 4 modules: 1) in the first one students will learn about how to engage all stakeholders of the target field for engagement to jointly design new solutions; 2) how to build a coherent strategy and vision to co-design innovative, sustainable and inclusive solutions to real problems through networking and knowledge sharing; 3) how to ensure the sustainability of innovation from the institutional, social and economic point of view by working together to build a viable strategy; 4) how to join forces between different points or nodes.

The last part of the lecture will focus on real case studies developed by two Living Labs related to sustainable and inclusive innovative management with citizens. Finally, the participants will be invited to reflect and come up with their own real cases.

4.3.2 Data/Technology driven innovation

Learning skills

- Business model innovation
- Data driven innovation
- Technology driven innovation
- Innovation as a key driver for economic and social growth

Lecture content

This lecture will examine business models - specifically technological and data-based models - in the context of the Innovation Typology course module. We will begin with a brief overview of business models - what they encompass and why they are a useful framework for viewing economic activity. The bulk of the course will look at recent key developments in business model innovations, and examine the social, industrial, economic and technological factors driving (or limiting) these changes. Is innovation - product or process-based - the only driver of economic and social growth? Are these two metrics ever in opposition? What are the implications of a shift from technological innovation to data innovation? We will pay particular attention to the interplay between stakeholder actors in the value chain: producers, users, and customers, and how their needs may drive innovation and change.

Part two of the lecture will look at the rising importance of data and technology as commodities, and how they have come to occupy a central position in today's economic production paradigm. This section will spotlight the challenges and successes posed by data-driven and technology-driven business models, including the social, financial, political and environmental consequences of these developments for producers and users alike.

The session is designed to be interactive in nature, and dialogue is encouraged. We will use a combination of case studies and exercises to illustrate particular points and explore the economic and social implications of innovation-driven business activity.

4.4 Stakeholder identification

4.4.1 Stakeholder identification

Learning skills

- Stakeholder engagement basics
- Degrees of user involvement and discussion from the perspective of the different user-centric designs
- 3-4-5 helix theory

Lecture content

This lecture aims to provide the essentials of the stakeholder engagement methodology within a Living Lab setting. This includes an analysis of the different categories of stakeholders (internal, external, primary, secondary, direct & indirect), the difference between stakeholder involvement and

engagement and the process to keep stakeholders' engagement over time within the Living Lab environment. 3-4-5 helix theory will also be explored in further detail compared to the previous lecture on the Living Lab methodology fundamentals. The panel management methodology will be also briefly introduced and will be further explored in Module 11. At the beginning of the session the game of the roulette of stakeholders with some entry questions will be introduced to the students to increase their interest and engagement. The main body of the lecture will provides a full set of knowledge about the fundamentals of the LL stakeholder engagement methodology. At the end of the session the instructor will ask open ended questions to the students to assess their increase of knowledge compared to the beginning of the session.

4.4.2 Open Innovation Ecosystems

Learning skills

- Open innovation ecosystems
- Multi-stakeholder approach for the orchestration of a Living Lab's interactions with other funding organisations, clusters, government, RTOs, large companies, SMEs, investors, business organisations, academia and policy makers
- Public-Private Partnership (PPP). LLs as "functional regions" enabling actors from companies, public entities, universities, institutes and individuals.

Lecture content

The lesson will focus on the Living Labs, funding organisations, Clusters, Government RTOs, Large Companies, SMEs, Investors, Business Organisations, Education & Training, Policy Makers, etc. through the application of open innovation strategies in the context of a regional innovation ecosystem.

In innovation ecosystems, inter-organisational collaboration is considered as a process of value creation in environmentally conditioned inter-organisational networks. Regional Economics literature focuses on the public-private interface, increasingly labelling intersectoral collaborative activities as 'open innovation' and using regional innovation systems as a model for describing them. Therefore, we will first examine how to link up the fields of Open Innovation, Innovation Ecosystems, and Regional Economics, and introduce a framework that combines the core propositions of these three theoretical perspectives with the aim to facilitate our understanding of the growing complexity of the open innovation practices in Living Labs.

Next, we will describe real cases about how the regionally embedded innovation ecosystems can be established and what the key elements of the Open Innovation strategy are. Next, we will provide a comparative overview of the core propositions of the Open Innovation, Innovation Ecosystems, and Regional Economics literature streams. Finally, we will use this framework and show how novel approaches to open innovation can be explained more effectively and we will draw some conclusions and discuss the implications for innovation researchers, living lab managers, private organizations and public policymakers.

4.4.3 Stakeholder analysis

Learning skills

Techniques and methods for stakeholder engagement.

Stakeholder mapping and analysis and identification

Lecture content

This lecture aims to provide a full representation of the available methods and techniques for stakeholder engagement within a Living Lab setting. This includes stakeholder analysis, mapping, stakeholder journey and a series of canvases and tools developed by ENoLL for stakeholder engagement within Living Labs. At the beginning of the session a short entry point quiz (multiple and closed answer) on stakeholder understanding and interaction will be provided to assess the knowledge of the participants prior to the start of the lesson. The lectures will provide a full set of knowledge about the fundamentals of the LL stakeholder engagement methodology. Then, the instructor will provide the stakeholder journey canvas for LLs developed by ENoLL and ask students to work on a set of fictional use cases to get a visual interpretation of the main targeted stakeholders. At the end of the session the instructor will ask open ended questions to the students to assess their increase of knowledge compared to the beginning of the session.

4.5 Needs assessment and problem definition

The Needs assessment and problem definition module will provide the skills to enable the students identifying user needs, scope the problem and find the opportunity for innovation

4.5.1 Needs analysis and problem identification

Learning skills

- Needs assessment and analysis.
- Learn to encouraging users to express their thoughts and attitudes towards the concepts being developed from the basis of their needs.
- Learn how to identify the (real) problem and the user needs.
- Turning problems into an opportunity for innovation.
- Co-designing solutions to community's problems.
- How to advocate for individual or community needs.

Lecture content

This lesson will focus on needs assessment and analysis, the ability to identify the community of stakeholders, the capacity to identify the real problem(s), the methodology of co-design, and finally, how to advocate for individual and community needs. The lesson will be divided in two main parts: the first will be dedicated to the difference between need assessment, need analysis and the importance of problem framing; the second half will focus on the methodology of co-design and on how to advocate the need of the community of reference.

The first part of the lesson will be dedicated to thoroughly explain the difference between need assessment (identify the need) and need analysis (identify the problem and how to overcome it), and the steps a team have to follow to conduct this kind of analysis (analyse the current situation, identify the objective, figure out the root of the problem, figure out how to solve it). Then the focus will be on the importance of correctly performing the problem framing, using dedicated templates to answer the following main questions: who is facing the problem; what the signals are indicating that this is a problem; when/where are the conditions under which we have observed the problem; and why do we think the problem happens. The participants will be invited to perform a need analysis using an interactive shared whiteboard.

The second half of the lesson will be dedicated to the methodology of co-design, as a process to implement what was discussed in the first part of the lesson (need assessment/analysis and problem framing) and understand how to identify the priority solutions. The focus will be on explaining what the co-design process is, its principles, what differentiates this approach from others by comparing co-design with other methodologies, how to implement the co-design in practice and all the tools available (e.g., conducting surveys or focus groups, hosting public events, users testing) and lastly, what co-design is not. An example of co-design in practice will be shown and discussed.

Finally, the lecture will cover the topic of advocate for individual and community needs, providing students with the tools to plan a needs assessment by identifying the community, describing the scope of the assessment, listing the question to ask, determining the data collection methods, reviewing and summarizing the data, developing a prioritization strategy for solving the identified problem. To conclude the lesson, students will be asked to collect ideas to perform a need assessment using an interactive shared whiteboard.

4.5.2 Techniques and tools for needs assessment

Learning skills

- Qualitative methods for living lab research: observation, survey, desktop research, interviews, etc.
- Need data analysis techniques
- Problem scoping
- Project future needs and trends
- Learn how established LLs can adopt the problem-solving approach to renew their surveys
- Look into problems from a different angle and redesign internal processes.

Lecture content

The first part of this lecture will focus on discussing techniques for need assessment while the second part will present use cases on how established living labs address problem solving.

In the first part of this lecture the students will learn about the basic principles of qualitative and quantitative research methods. After the course students should be able to plan, set up, carry out a research study (quant. and qual.) and how to analyse the gathered data. Moreover, they should know the basic principles and methodologies of qual./quant. research.

In the introduction session students will learn about the main paradigms, i.e., Positivism as main worldview behind quantitative research (Testing hypotheses (deductive), collecting facts as basis for

laws (inductive), objective and value free science) and Interpretivism as main worldview and basis for many qualitative approaches (meaning is constructed not discovered). Theoretical positions such as phenomenology, symbolic interaction or ethnomethodology will be touched laying the theoretical foundations. Moreover, classical quality criteria, reliability, validity, objectivity (stemming from quantitative research) and how these criteria are applied in qualitative research is discussed and alternative criteria such as credibility will be debated within this course.

After the introduction, example methods will be discussed, i.e., qualitative interview, group discussion, focus group, observation, survey. Based on one concrete example (qualitative interview) students should learn how to plan and set-up a qualitative research study, how the data is gathered (conducting a qualitative interview), how data is prepared for the analyses (e.g., transcription) and how data is interpreted/analysed (e.g., coding & understanding). In groups of four, students will be asked to plan, carry out and analyse a small interview by their own. This process should allow students to better understand the techniques through “learning by doing”. There will be two main communication channels, i.e., Discord (chat, video/voice calls in group work) and Webex for lecture parts and presentations. Moreover, interactive tools, such as Miro will be used for brainstorming, feedback and for exchanging thoughts.

The second part of the lecture will focus on living lab methods that can be used for needs assessment, beyond the commonly known methods such as (online) surveys, desk research, workshops and focus groups. A very specific method, known as Human Factors Study, will be presented, together with some examples use cases to show how to implement this method in practice. We will highlight when to use this methodology, what the benefits are as well as the constraints.

The following use cases will be presented:

- Smart pill dispenser
- Smart medication blister
- Remote rehabilitation game

4.6 Survey, interview and focus group methodologies in user centric research

This module will learn the students to conduct survey, interview and focus group methods in the Living Lab context.

4.6.1 An introduction to qualitative inquiry, quantitative and mixed methods in research using a Living Lab approach

Learning skills

- Typology of research qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods
- Background research to align what researchers want to make with what users want to use.
- Desktop research and state of the art
- Validated survey instruments in user centric research
- Key principles, guidelines and rules for engagement

Lecture content

This lesson will focus on how to conduct studies in user centric research. For this purpose, the lesson will cover the following main topics: the differences between the 3 different research approaches that are quantitative, qualitative and the mixed method, with a focus on quantitative research and methods for validation of the quantitative instruments; the importance of background research; how to conduct desktop research and how to identify the state-of-the-art; the guidelines rules of stakeholder's engagement.

The lecture will open with an overview of the three research approaches: quantitative, qualitative and the mixed methods. The distinctive characteristics of the three approaches will be discussed, along with the specific instruments and techniques used to conduct the studies, the specific type of research questions they can address, and finally their pros and cons. Then the participants will be asked to try to match the right methods and its techniques with some proposed research questions with a real time interactive quiz.

Next the lesson will focus on the quantitative method and in particular on the meaning and importance of validation of the instruments created (e.g., questionnaires, surveys, usability tests etc.), as a way to assess the accuracy of a quantitative instrument from two main point of you, external validity (possibility to generalize from a sample to a population) and content validity (appropriateness of the content), based on the research question.

Then, the second part of the lecture will focus on the importance of conducting a quick but effective background research, identifying and describing the history, root, nature and context of the research problem being addressed and how previous studies have investigated it. Since background research does not replace the literature review, the next step will be to give the students the basic information on how to conduct desktop research (secondary research), namely, how to review existing research for obtaining relevant information. In detail the lesson will focus on how to identify specific, useful and relevant qualitative and/or quantitative data; how to develop an understanding of the current policy and business needs; and how to identify gaps in existing data. Conducting desktop research will allow to define the current state-of-the-art, so the development stage from which to understand how a project may contribute to expand knowledge.

Lastly, the lecture will be dedicated to 3 C's of successful stakeholders engagement: Collaboration, Consultation, and Communication. To conclude, participants will be invited to discuss how to engage different types of stakeholders with an interactive shared whiteboard.

4.6.2 Practical guidelines for Survey, interview and focus group methodologies in user centric research

Learning skills

- Qualitative Individual interview techniques in user centric research
- Focus group interview techniques in user centric research
- Online survey tools
- Crowdsourcing as the collection of information from a group of people

Lecture content

The lecture will focus on offline and online user centric qualitative research methods, such as online survey tools, interview and focus group methodologies, and quantitative surveys in order to systemize the modes of integration of users' experiences in Living Lab innovation processes, with special focus on the key principles that are considered crucial in Living Lab operations: continuity, openness, realism, empowerment of users, and spontaneity. The concept and method of interviewing is going to be presented as a sociocultural practice, which involves a specific "field of communicability" – a social construction of communicative processes with its own purposes, contextualities and interpretational possibilities.

The differences between structured, unstructured and semi-structured interview forms are going to be discussed in detail, supported with user centric interview examples as implemented in different Living Lab operation phases (idea, concept, prototype, test). Next, focus group methodology is going to be presented, with special attention to sampling, scripting, facilitating dialogue, fostering feedback and interpreting user behaviour and user narratives. Different forms of grouping, sampling and organizing will be discussed through examples from Living Lab research actions (from user moderated to online and two-way focus groups). Finally, different usages of online survey are going to be presented as a method capable of realizing a broad variety of user involvement practices from user comments and ratings of the presented ideas, concepts and prototypes to users posting product revisions or alternate product suggestions.

Attention will be drawn to the recent shift from user-centric online surveys towards community-centric involvement. As part of the latter, the method of crowdsourcing will be elaborated in detail, a tool that requires sustained human involvement and applied in order to motivate users to boost innovation, or to complete data processing tasks that computing technology has yet to master accurately. Its various forms will be illustrated by examples from gamification to human computation and grand challenges, emphasizing its potential to turn conventional content management applications into social machines in which tasks are performed as optimal combinations of human and computational intelligence.

The central concepts of crowdsourcing, such as open call, wisdom of the crowds, Web 2.0, mass collaboration, collective intelligence will be highlighted. Questions, such as "What to crowdsource?", "Who is the crowd?", "How to crowdsource?", "How to define the target audience?", "How to incentivize?", "How to identify suitable engagement mechanisms?", "How to determine a technical platform to support activities?" will be addressed through real-life Living Lab crowdsourcing examples applying the Motive-Incentive-Activation-Behaviour model of crowdsourcing.

4.7 Co-creation sessions Ideation, conceptualization and prototyping techniques

The target of this module is to give the ability to the students to understand and use co-creation techniques for ideating, concept creation and prototyping.

4.7.1 Idea, concept and prototype in implementation science

Learning skills

- Understanding similarities and differences between idea, concept and prototype
- Implementation science

Lecture content

During this lecture and within the first part the understanding of the similarities and differences among idea, concept and prototype will be presented while the second part will focus on the implementation science.

During this lecture, the core Living Lab methodology is going to be briefly presented, discussing both its theoretical and methodological underpinnings (Soft Systems Thinking, Appreciative Inquiry, NeedFinding), and the different iteration flows that can be implemented in each phase (i.e., cycles, such as understanding-generating-evaluating; appreciate opportunities-design-evaluate).

Particular attention will be drawn to how FormIT is fundamentally different from traditional problem-solving approaches as an iterative process based on interaction with users, which is a prerequisite of design thinking: knowledge increases through iterative interactions between phases and people with diverse competences and perspectives. Of the 5 different phases of FormIT (Planning/idea, Concept design, Prototype design, Innovation design, Commercialization), the first 3 phases are going to be presented in detail. In the context of the Planning/idea phase the value of different user competencies will be emphasized for stimulating knowledge sharing and increasing understanding of the involved stakeholders' visions; tools for supporting continuous communication and building trust and confidence between the stakeholders are going to be presented through examples.

As for the conceptualization phase, focus will be put on the appreciation of opportunities and on generating the basic needs that different stakeholders have of the product or service (studying the "current state" of users; identifying the problem; matching a new solution to the problem while taking into account the specific contexts in which these problems occur). It is going to be presented through real-life Living Lab examples, that this cycle should end up in a concept, which represents the generated needs from the first step in the cycle: so that in the conceptualization phase there is a clear shift from generating needs to designing concepts. Particular attention will be drawn to the five Key Principles (value, influence, sustainability, openness, realism) to consider how value can be created for the users, how the users can influence the process, how sustainability take form in this project, how openness should take form and how the process should be designed to capture as realistic situation as possible.

Lastly, the prototyping phase is going to be discussed in detail with special focus on how a prototype is built in order to represent a product or experience before the actual artefact is completed, and how the experimentation stage puts the designed solution to the test, as much as possible in a real-life context. A variety of data gathering methods will be presented that can facilitate this phase, such as interviews and observations, as well as tools to include basic functions, workflows, and interfaces, so that the prototype will be detailed enough for the users to understand and be able to experience how the final service will look and feel.

The second part will focus on the while the second part will focus on the implementation science through knowledge transformation. KT practitioners and researchers have been called to draw from different disciplines (e.g. sociology, psychology), theories (e.g. learning, behaviour change, organizational) and frameworks (e.g. KT process models; determinant frameworks) to explain and predict health care professionals' behavior, change or adherence to a new practice, and implementation outcomes (Brehaut and Eva, 2012; Colquhoun et al., 2010). This is particularly helpful given the numerous challenges associated with KT processes; indeed, human behaviour is complex and health care professionals function within complex and evolving contexts. In keeping with IS's main objective, interventions used to promote the uptake of scientific knowledge must be grounded in theoretical frameworks, they must be developed using robust methods and should consider the different stakeholders who can endorse EIHPE within a specific context (Lapaige,

2010). When used appropriately, different theories (Nielsen et al., 2015a) can enhance conceptual clarity, specify hypothesized relationships between constructs, identify determinants of change/research use, inform data collection and data analysis, specify implementation processes and/or outcomes and guide implementation planning (Birken et al., 2017; Hull et al., 2019)

Following these modules learners will be able to:

- Differentiate between the basic concepts, and terminologies used in KT
- Describe the stages of the knowledge translation process
- Apply the stages of the KT process for a project/study in their own context
- Describe implementation science and compare/contrast it to KT
- Describe the main theories and conceptual models that can be in each of the steps of the KT process

4.7.2 Co-creation and workshop facilitation techniques

Learning skills

- Workshop planning and timing (dos and don'ts).
- Workshop facilitation techniques.
- Bring together researchers and stakeholders into the prototyping space through co-creation workshops.
- Ice breaker techniques.
- Co-creation techniques for ideation and conceptualization in workshop settings.
- Techniques to conceptualize and prototype.

Lecture content

In this lecture the best practices, techniques and tools (e.g. personas, scenarios, mock-ups, image boarding, staged interviews, collaborative diaries, ice-breaking practices, and think aloud) of Co-creative Workshops will be presented, with a special focus on involving and engaging stakeholders and end-users in the creative atmosphere of prototyping space. It is going to be illustrated through examples how latent end-user needs can be uncovered, as during Co-Creative Workshops a large amount of data is generated that are meant to evoke empathy for the stakeholders and end-users involved, and to inform and inspire the innovation process.

Crucial aspects of organizing Co-creative Workshops will be discussed, such as preparation (defining the context and a clear objective for the workshop to identify the participants properly); facilitating (as the success of co-creative workshops depends on the facilitator and co-facilitator, who is able to oversee the whole process and leave enough space for creativity whilst keeping an eye on the objective); sampling (selecting and gathering participants is crucial, and it is of utmost importance to invite a mixture of participants with different expertise fields, i.e. users as experts of their own experiences and characters, e.g. realist, innovator, creator, etc.; planning (as defining the workshop activities and the duration of each of the activities, it helps coordinating the organization and facilitation of a Co-Creative Workshop); organizing space (so to stimulate creativity, and to make participants feel at ease); and data capturing and consent (since during a Co-Creative Workshop, a

large amount of information is generated and capturing the data of the workshop can be crucial for further phases through video, audio and pictures.

During the next part of the lecture the four phases of a Co-Creative Workshop is going to be presented and simulated with the students: Co-analysis (where participants analyse the context to explore possibilities, define use cases and generate solution spaces), Co-design (where participants give shape to the solution generated in the Co-analysis phase by defining the main functionalities of the solution), Co-evaluation (where participants evaluate the solution generated in the Co-design phase by means of stakeholder values) and Co-implementation (where participants define the implementation process, with the aim to identify the factors of influence on a decision to adopt the solution or to reject it). At the end of this section of the lecture tools and techniques will be presented for documenting and communicating the insights and findings generated throughout a Co-Creative Workshop.

4.7.3 Tools for Co-creation and Open Innovation sessions

Learning skills

- Tools and virtual spaces to run online workshop
- Techniques to ideate
- Creativity boosting techniques
- Design sprint, open innovation camps and hackathons
- Obtain awareness of different types of fast paced co-creation sprint events and their key characteristics
- Learn key skills to plan (pre-event), manage (during the event) and report (post-event) sprint events
- Apply theories in practice by creating own sprint event plan

Lecture content

The lecture will provide an overview of different types of fast paced competitive and non-competitive co-creation sprint events. The included in-depth online and offline event examples in various thematical topics consist e.g. Google design sprint, Hackathon, open innovation camp and Service jam. Examples of timelines, key activities and tools are provided for planning (pre-event), managing (during the event) and reporting (post-event) sprint events. Links to literature (academic and professional articles) to be announced later.

During this lecture tools and techniques are going to be shared with regards to facilitating innovation process through workshops with special focus on virtual collaboration, and on ideation techniques as well (provocation, storyboard, brainstorming, brainwriting, worst possible idea, game storming, crazy 8's, mash-up, etc). The differences between traditional workshops and ideation workshops are going to be discussed, as the latter differs in that those are based on sufficient user research and have a clear problem statement, take place in judgement-free evaluative settings and introduce new stimuli, and hence spark innovation through lateral thinking is key, and by focusing on quantity rather than quality of ideas.

The benefits of such teamwork techniques are going to be discussed in detail (better team cohesion, increased trust, greater understanding, improved brainstorming, better engagement) with special

attention to its creativity-boosting aspect, that stems from the judgement-free character of ideation techniques, which fosters team members to bring unique perspectives and experiences to the table. In the following part, the possibilities and benefits of remote workshops and virtual collaborative spaces (video conferencing solutions, whiteboarding, cloud file storage, cooperative virtual realities) are going to be discussed as it is crucial to choose the right platforms to support team building, problem solving, and ideation, even if the team isn't co-located.

Among the collaborative virtual spaces for running workshops special focus will be put on online whiteboard tools (Miro, Mural, Stormboard), which allow for the group's creativity to flow by working on the same whiteboard, offer an endless flexible space where the team can collaborate and share ideas; collaboration tools (Trello, Todoist, Asana), to address the challenge of long to-do-lists having multiple facilitation assignments, most teams are facing today; note taking apps and tools for organizing information (Evernote, Microsoft OneNote, Google Drive, Notion), as noting down various bits of information during a session design process is crucial, especially when talking with clients; engagement tools and meeting facilitation softwares (Stormz, MeetButter, Axis, MentiMeter, Sli.do), for quickly polling the opinions of all participants, sharing and elaborating participants' opinion on the subject at hand, and surveying qualitative insights from group members - a meeting facilitation software allows participants to easily interact with each other can be useful in such cases; online design tools (Canva, Figma, Invision), which allows for collaboratively working on visual assets for product and marketing initiatives.

The small group assignment (group size 3 to 5 depending on total number of students) includes planning of (A) online or (B) offline co-creation sprint event to the one of the following innovation type: (1) digital or physical product innovation or (2) digital or physical service innovation. Furthermore, plan must address relevant sustainability issues relating the selected sprint and innovation type.

The plan consisting pre-during-post phases is documented into Miro whiteboard. During the group work, teams will communicate via conference meeting system such as Google meets, Zoom or Teams. Afterwards, as an individual task student are (1) peer-reviewing one of the other groups plan with the help of provided template and (2) doing self and peer evaluation of regarding own group work.

4.8 Testing experimentation and validation techniques

This module will aim at the understanding of the different types of testing methods the ability to formulate testing plan and conduct testing for different types of tests

4.8.1 Typology of testing

Learning skills

Typology of testing: idea, concept, feasibility, prototype, usability, real life testing

Testing and intervention planning, procedures and management

Lecture content

This lecture has not been clarified yet. The content will be added on a later stage.

4.8.2 Living Labs as Research Infrastructures

Learning skills

Online and Offline testing methods and tools: Idea testing, concept testing, prototype testing, feasibility/usability testing, real-life testing, proof-of-concept.

Testbeds, Living Labs as Research Infrastructures, Living Labs as Technology Infrastructures

Lecture content

During this session we will explain and focus on the importance of research infrastructures for the success of our innovations emphasising its role as validation and testing facilities. We will start the class with an overview of the main difference between a living lab and a testbed and how we can leverage the latter for the development of new products/services. We will then clarify the purpose of these research infrastructures, what they look like, what services they offer, what their capabilities are and what their flexibility is with respect to serving different stakeholders.

Finally, within these infrastructures we will emphasise the role of technology, what its role is and how it can help us to improve the processes of development, testing and commercialisation of our innovations, while complying with the regulations of the target market.

4.9 Research ethics, legal issues, data management and protection

The module will foster the ability to execute living lab research in ethical way, GDPR requirements and any other national legislations as well as to create data management plan and foster open data principles.

4.9.1 Basic Ethics Concepts

Learning skills

- Basic ethics concepts
- Dimensions of Ethics: Meta-Ethics, Prescriptive Ethics (Normative Ethics), Descriptive Ethics (Comparative Ethics) and Applied Ethics
- GDPR issues
- Informed consent (legal requirements and examples for different contextual settings)

Lecture content

The lesson will start with an engagement exercise to explore individual understandings and complement the views among the class through the questioning of “What is ethics and what is it for?”, “Why is it so crucial to have a stance towards a constant reflection in actions in any field of life, and specifically in research?”. Following a tour on relevant concepts will take place, including the concept of Ethics, Ethos, Morality, and the branches of Ethics, including Meta-Ethics (ethics about ethics), Prescriptive Ethics or so called Normative Ethics and its different sub-branches (deontological ethics, teleological, and virtue ethics), Descriptive Ethics or so called Comparative Ethics (dealing with people and society beliefs among morality) and Applied Ethics (dealing with ethical questions specific to practical fields, and include bio ethics, legal ethics, business ethics,

medical ethics, etc.). Origin and impulse of Bioethics and the importance of the social debate with the sharing of two cases of Clinical bioethics put to the test on which the students may elaborate. It follows a brief assessment of understanding with different statements that students should analyse and connect with the corresponding Branch of Ethics, working, if possible, in small groups.

In the second half of the lecture the focus will be on the research practice, specifically on the straight relation among responsible research and innovation and ethics, and among ethics and best clinical practices, or ethics and privacy, with many more relations that can be named. These relations will ensure the students have in mind that ethics is a constant challenge a professional need to deal, and that the work for excellence and with best practices along with the development of a personal ethical identity are the key for answer the challenges. Specifically emerging ethical issues in living labs (e.g. based on research production of authors such Fausto J. Sainz, 2012) will be explored, and Privacy and ethics in Living Labs from the literature and shared lessons. The students will be called to create a matrix of DO's/MUSTS and DONT's from the presented cases. The lesson finalizes with a practical and assessment exercise in which, through storytelling methodology, roleplaying or other creative approach pairs of students represent a situation that might be frequent in R&I (previously defined in small groups of students) in which one or more ethical dimensions should be discussed, analysed and a final scenario of ethical fulfilment (without conflict by the parts) presented.

The lecture will follow a three-pronged approach: (a) general introduction to personal data protection; (b) understanding the principles, obligations and requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679) and (c) the privacy by design frame.

The lecture start with a participatory exercise brainstorming key words and principles related with data protection regulation to explore the actual knowledge of the class, followed by an analysis of the different key concepts that should be elucidated such as Personal Data, Data Protection, Data Privacy (that addresses the proper storage, access, retention, immutability and security of sensitive data), Data Confidentiality (protecting data against unintentional, unlawful, or unauthorized access, disclosure, or theft), and Consent, and rules and/or guidelines for their management. With these clearer concepts, a moment of reflection on their importance.

The second part will be focused on exploring principles, obligations and requirements of the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC. Starting with what Data Protection stands for, as a set of strategies to secure the privacy, availability, and integrity of data (protect people, their privacy, their right to privacy, their right to own and protect their data, to choose what can be shared and with who, in which conditions, for how long, and to which extent). GDPR will be presented through an applied exploration of the key components (Data minimisation, Accuracy, Storage limitation, Integrity and confidentiality (security)) followed by GDPR Consent Examples. Next, the Core Principles of the GDPR (Lawfulness, fairness and transparency; Purpose limitation; Data minimisation; Accuracy; Storage limitation; Integrity and confidentiality (security); Accountability) will be stated and explored in simulated cases that will help to understand the Consent Requirements for different situations, when is consent appropriate, what is a valid consent. At the end of the exercise students should define the type of consent that fits the case they have in hands and its main requirements (e.g. who is involved in the research, what data uses/collects, what type of information should be provided to the research subject, paper or mobile user consent, singular considerations when involving children, imaging procedures, incapacitated adults not able to give informed consent, illiterate populations, who should give the information/ how to inform). During the process, it will be emphasized the importance of a thoughtful point of view the General Data

Protection Regulation (GDPR), as the considered the most comprehensive security and privacy law worldwide and understood by many as one of the world's strictest. A deconstruction exercise will be encouraged once, while protecting natural persons and their rights, the Regulation also acknowledges the reality that organizations need data to function properly. Students will be able to state examples of applicability in which the "norms" should apply, and in which a particular data processing prohibited by default can be allowed, which means that under certain conditions, the prohibitions introduced by the Regulation shall not apply. Yet, consequences of non-compliance with GDPR will also be approached.

Finally, the Privacy by design will be introduced as to merge the knowledge discussed during 9.1.1 and 9.1.2 into an applicability frame of data protection through technology design. It includes understand what is and what value it has a focus on Privacy by design (that includes different pillars on Privacy requirements of systems; Privacy engineering; Privacy design strategies; Privacy design patterns; Privacy enhancing technologies - PETS). The Foundational Principles of Privacy by Design will be presented and discussed since it is essential to ensure compliance with European and national legislation on the protection of personal data during the design and execution of a research project. In small groups students will be challenged to select and explore one of the different study cases and the strategies implemented and wrapping-up connecting the learning.

4.9.2 IPR and copyright in open innovation

Learning skills

- IPR and copyright in open innovation projects
- Intellectual property arising from the research collaboration
- Publications and transfers or research results
- Ethical application and ethical committees
- MDR (medical device regulation)

Lecture content

The assets of institutions and firms consist of two main elements; tangible and intangible assets. Knowledge assets form a significant part of intangible assets. Knowledge assets, like all assets, have owner(s) who seek to exploit, develop and protect them. The knowledge that forms the basis of the asset is essentially composed of two parts; explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge.

In the first part of this lesson, we will describe the elements of the knowledge assets and their interrelationship. Since knowledge assets are essentially intangible assets, they can only be protected by legal means. In the first part, we will familiarize students with the main legal frameworks and the logic of their application, which can be essentially divided into two parts; IPR (Industrial Property Right) and Copy Right.

In the second part of the lesson, we will introduce their application in open innovation and research projects. We will analyze the different IPR and Copy Right options for research and innovation. We will also show how research collaboration can help to increase intellectual property (intellectual capital). We will also point out the specific problems that open innovation raises in the area of IPR and Copy Right and show how these problems can be addressed.

4.9.3 FAIR data and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

Learning skills

- Open and FAIR data principles
- Responsible Research and Innovation
- Data management planning
- Data protection
- Data anonymization
- Identify data sources

Lecture content

The lesson will provide an introduction to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) as a concept used in the EU 's Framework Programme to describe research and technological development from the viewpoint of its impact on society and the environment. This will include the FAIR data principles⁴ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)

Data Management Planning (DMP) will involve acquiring know-how on how to create a plan on data management, including protecting your data and anonymizing it (e. g. guidelines of the Academy of Finland)⁵. Data literacy will be discussed in connection with data source identification.

The assignments will involve individual and group work via the digital learning platform Canvas and Zoom conferencing system (incl. breakout group work). Quiz on theoretical aspects of RRI and open and FAIR data principles (individual work). Group presentations on theoretical aspects data literacy, protection and anonymization. Task in data management planning (DMP) (in groups).

4.10 User / research panel management

This module will provide the theoretical foundations of user/research panel management

4.10.1 User research & Panel management

Learning skills

- Ability recruit and manage user panels.
- User panel management (online vs. offline).
- Recruiting and maintaining strategies (do and don't).
- Sample selection including inclusion and exclusion strategies.
- Utilization of commercial market research panels.

⁴ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>

⁵ <https://www.aka.fi/en/research-funding/apply-for-funding/how-to-apply-for-funding/az-index-of-application-guidelines2/data-management-plan/data-management-plan/>

Lecture content

This online lesson looks at panel management in all its aspects. First, the benefits but also the limitations of a panel are highlighted. A panel can drive a living lab and enables end-user involvement. The panel has valuable input through co-creation and co-design. On the other hand, one should always keep a critical eye on which panelists are included in living lab activities. The participants should be as diverse and as closely aligned with the intended audience as possible.

This lesson shares the experience of LiCalab, a living lab in Belgium, in setting up and further developing the panel. Setting up a panel begins with recruitment. Several strategies for recruitment are highlighted. Participants are then invited, using a Miro board, to list possible recruitment strategies that can be applied in their own context. These are discussed as a group so that ideas can be exchanged. Once the user panel is in place, it has to be managed. This requires a dedicated panel manager within the living lab team who is also the SPOC for the panelists. A relationship of trust, promotes the commitment of the panel members. An appropriate sample should be included for each project and activity. Keeping panel members engaged requires understanding panelists' motivators and thresholds. Panelists can be approached both online and offline. Both are necessary to achieve the greatest possible diversity. During the pandemic, LiCalab built experience in online co-creation. These experiences are shared extensively during class and discussed further in group.

Secondly, a well-managed user panel can be a source of data that can be used in a smart way. In this way, member profiles can be further segmented and enriched. During the lesson attention is paid to possible software tools to capture such data. The group will interactively discuss which data are useful to monitor and under what conditions. This of course depends on the purpose and focus of the living lab. Informed consent and privacy rules should be respected. During this class, participants are invited to translate the theoretical concepts into their own practice. A Miro board provides the guide to capture all experiences and ideas.

4.10.2 Panel members profiling

Learning skills

- Unlimited and extended profiling can be done by having panel members signup and take surveys for profiling
- Option to communicate with members via email

Lecture content

This lecture has not been clarified yet. The content will be added on a later stage.

4.10.3 Panel engagement and panel data

Learning skills

- Export/import panelist data
- Search/filter panel members.
- Panel update, motivations and dropout strategies.
- Road mapping for panel engagement

Lecture content

This lecture has not been clarified yet. The content will be added on a later stage.

4.11 Living lab project planning and management

The module will provide the knowledge required for defining a project plan for a living lab project

4.11.1 Research design for own "user centric project"

Learning skills

- Research design for own "user centric project"
- Intervention planning via template

Lecture content

This lecture has not been clarified yet. The content will be added on a later stage.

4.11.2 Innovation projects and activities carried out within a Living Lab

Learning skills

- Refer to the innovation projects and activities carried out within a living lab.
- Work on entrepreneurial or research project.
- Gain experience in transforming an idea into a sustainable business model.

Lecture content

The lesson will focus on the different innovation projects according to the activities that can be possibly carried out in a Living Lab. The four stages of innovation process, including the concept creation, mock-up testing, small scale pilot testing, and full-scale market launch, will be used as the basic for planning innovation projects within a Living Lab.

Within the first stage, concept creation and testing phase, co-creating unique proposition-based users' needs and analysis, and high level concept testing will be discussed. In the second stage, mock-up testing phase, explanation on how to verify and prioritize the use case scenarios for further development and verification will be provided. Afterwards, within the third stage, small scale pilot testing, the lesson will focus on how evaluate feasibility, time cost, adverse events, and improve upon the study design prior to full-scale field testing. Finally, information will be provided on how reliability and scalability are tested at the system level within the Living Lab.

Next, according to each innovation process phase (e.g., need, challenge and opportunity identification, idea generation and idea testing, concepting and prototyping, product and service development, validation and impact assessment, market scalability and post-market), the aim behind these phases and the key activities to be performed in each of them will be analysed.

During this lecture, different tools and techniques of Living lab methodology are going to be applied through individual work for analysing, reflecting on and developing one's own entrepreneurial or research project. First the 3-layer model and the quadruple helix are going to be used to map the

different contexts one's own project is embedded in. To get into more details, Living Lab roles, actors, responsibilities, and services will be analysed in the context of each project with a special focus on users: students will draft empathy maps and personas with regards to their project, fostering the transformation of their project into a sustainable business model. At the end of the lecture students will present their analyses and reflections to the group for collaborative thinking.

4.12 Entrepreneurship

This module will provide the knowledge for collaborating effectively with a Living Lab's team and generate ideas that drive innovation and entrepreneurship.

4.12.1 Transforming an idea into a sustainable business model

Learning skills

- Transforming an idea into a sustainable business model.
- Create measurable positive impact on society and the environment.
- Business Plan.
- Business case examples.

Lecture content

Once relegated to the side-lines of business theory, impact, or social, entrepreneurship is rising in stature. Growing awareness of the need to meet our existential challenges is leading many established companies to re-examine or adapt their business models. Many aspiring entrepreneurs now seek a viable pathway to develop their ideas into a sustainable business that can have both positive fiscal and social impact.

This session will explore what is necessary to build a sustainable, impact-driven business. We will begin by examining the factors that differentiate social entrepreneurship, how those factors are measured, and how such businesses are evaluated for viability, scalability, and investability. We will also consider various forms of incorporation, such as B Corp, that may influence a business' trajectory. Following this, we will look at case studies of three proven impact business models. These examples can draw attention to the following: How and why are impact businesses different from traditional entrepreneurial ventures? What additional challenges do impact-based companies face as they validate their product, build traction, seek investment? How can an impact orientation make a business stronger or more resilient to changes in the external business environment (economic, social, political, technological)? What are the relative roles of the founder, the user, the customer and the investor in driving positive change? Are these roles ever in conflict? Throughout the course, we will test various products that can aid the development and evaluation of a social impact business plan, including canvas-type templates, platforms, and other tools and frameworks. The lecture will be interactive and dialogue is encouraged.

4.12.2 How LL services can accelerate access to the market

Learning skills

- How LL services can accelerate access to the market.

Lecture content

The lesson will focus on how the Living Labs can accelerate access to the market. It highlights the critical role that Living Labs can play in helping Living Lab researchers reduce the time it takes to move from product idea to the market. Understanding the concept of Time to Market is an excellent initial step. Time to Market is the duration needed to bring a product to fruition. This includes the generation of an idea for the product; its whole design cycle; development and launch on the market.

The more streamlined and effective the product development process is, the better a researcher is able to predict the time to market. This can assist in making plans on how to roll-out the product at the right place and time. The goal is to improve the time to market through different Living Lab activities.

How can Living Labs accelerate the time to market? The following are some ways to accelerate access to the market. Living Labs can teach: a) how to integrate innovation into the product development lifecycle, b) how to think of a revenue goal or target, c) how to develop markets or a segment of customers where the product innovations can be piloted with an acceptable risk level, d) how to automate the product development stage, e) how to develop ways to track results effectively.

The capacity to reduce the time to market for innovations and the ways this can be achieved is the key lesson learnt through this module. After this lesson researchers will be able to learn how their product can reach out to consumers as soon as possible giving an edge over competitors.

4.13 Sustainability

4.13.1 LL Labeling framework (ENoLL Evaluation)

Learning skills

- LL labeling framework (ENoLL)
- Measuring living lab's impact
- Learn the way in which LLs contribute to sustainability transitions (SDGs Sustainable Development Goals)

Lecture content

The lesson will focus on the Living Labs evaluation criteria, the Living Labs evaluation methodology, the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure impact and how to collect a living lab's KPIs as well as on putting the participants in the shoes of the evaluation committee. The differences between the evaluation and the impact of living labs will be presented. Starting from the evaluation, the importance of it for the living labs will be explained. In addition, the evaluation procedure prerequisites, including common understanding of the living lab methodologies and principles, common evaluation criteria, clear understanding on how to evaluate the different criteria, will be discussed.

Next, the importance of certification will be presented followed by the description of the evaluation criteria. More focus will be on the organization of living labs and more specifically to the management and governance, operations and ability to participated in innovation system mechanisms criteria. The user and reality evaluation criteria will touch the iterative living lab process, the people engagement approach and the quality of methods and tools. The roles and responsibilities of staff,

and access and availability of infrastructures and the communication strategy will be presented in the resource's evaluation criteria. The Openness of and IPRs along with the co-created value and coverage of the value chain will be presented in the Openness and Value evaluation criteria. Finally, the business mode and future plans evaluation criteria will be discussed. For all the above-mentioned criteria, a weighting system will be explained. The common mistakes and misunderstandings will conclude the evaluation criteria topic. At this point, the participants will be invited to evaluate a living lab by going through an anonymized application.

The second half of the lecture will focus on the importance of measuring a living lab's impact through KPIs, explaining that the KPIs allow living lab managers to get an overview of how their living lab is performing as well as that it allows for actionable metrics. How to set KPIs in order to drive impact of the living labs activities and the model of SMART KPIs will be presented. Some KPIs for Governance, Business model, Culture, Human Resources, living lab operations, equipment and infrastructure, Innovations, ownership of results, user centricity and lifecycle experimentation approach will be explained. Finally, the participants will be invited to reflect and come up with their own KPIs for a living lab

4.13.2 Living Lab Business Model, Business Plan and Sustainability

Learning skills

- Living Lab Business Model.
- Living Lab Business Plan.
- Sustainability and scalability of LL.

Lecture content

The first part of the lecture will focus on the living lab business model and business plan while the second part will touch upon the sustainability and scalability of living labs.

The lesson will focus on presenting and co-creating the Business model of a Living Lab. The Business Modelling Canvas methodology will be explained. The lesson will describe how a Living Lab creates, delivers and captures value. A thorough examination of the available business models/strategies for similar organisations will be presented. A business modelling co-creation workshop will be conducted to present the LL business model. Feedback will be received. The core LL business model will be presented and validated.

The LL business areas that will be presented concern the produce, customers, infrastructures and financial aspects. On the products front, the value proposition will identify what the value of a living lab is. The customer segments corresponds to the groups of people or organizations LLs wants to offer value to, the customer relationships to the relationships LLs establish with its customers while the channels deal with the way LLs communicate with and reach their customers in order to deliver a value proposition. On the infrastructure side, the key activities have to do with the most important activities that LLs must perform in order to make their business model work, the key resources as the most important assets (tangible and intangible) that LLs require to make their business model work and the key partners that are important for consideration in order to make the business model work. The financial aspects deal with the revenue streams (the ways in which LLs generate revenue) and the cost structure (all the costs incurred to operate the business model).

Finally, the business plan of a Living Lab will be presented. The lecture will explain the business strategy of a LL and the key goals to get from where they are now to where they want to be in the future. It will outline LL strategies across the business, including financial projections, marketing and operational plans (e.g. business description, market analysis, competitor analysis, operations and management plan). Real case examples will be presented.

The scalability methodology focuses on increasing the number of people who can benefit from the innovations developed in the project, offering practical advice on how to carry out each of the steps and tasks necessary for effective scalability: select projects with the potential if scaled, design projects to maximize their scalability, and manage the scalability process.

To this end, this second part of the lecture will pursue the following objectives: 1) determine the potential for business, marketing, research and mentoring opportunities of the project results; 2) establishment of a sustainable ecosystem of a project and its results; 3) definition and implementation of the exploitation and innovation plan and support to the entities in their exploitation of the relevant results of the project; 4) definition of business models both locally and globally and identification of possible innovation opportunities, both internal and external for the sustainability of the project's ecosystem; 5) monitor and analyse the exploitation and innovation potential of the project for the exploitation of the project results; 6) definition and development of the scalability methodology and replication plan to ensure the sustainability of the project results.

The methodology presented in this process will consist of three steps and ten tasks that will help in the scalability mechanism. The description of each task will be supported by the presentation of different tools and case studies that will help to understand the methodology. Finally, after the review of the tasks, the support tools and the case studies, the participants will be asked to apply the methodology in their own project.

4.13.3 Pitfalls in open innovation towards a sustainable Living Lab ecosystem

Learning skills

- Methods and examples on how a Living Lab can be open to innovation coming from its ecosystem.
- The governance of the living labs and how easily any stakeholder can go through your LL for their innovation.

Lecture content

During the first half of this class, we will discuss the evolution from triple helix to quintuple helix. What the transition has been like and what lessons it has taught us for the living lab context and how to incorporate it to take our innovations to the next level. In the same way, we will learn about the methods implicit in them and how to implement them in the governance of living lab infrastructures.

Then, we will navigate in depth over four case examples that will illustrate very significantly how this theory has been implemented and what has been achieved for the benefit of it. However, we will end the session (the second half) by reflecting on some of the pitfalls that have been made, which also provide us with positive results for moving forward.

4.13.4 Realistic Evaluation

Learning skills

- Evaluation and sustainability
- Realistic Evaluation

Lecture content

This course will focus on evaluating and measuring impact: educational, social, ecological and economic impact. It will examine how the ability to communicate with the stakeholder community relates to the sustainability of the LLs. The course will then address how to support a realistic evaluation.

The lecture will also cover the topic of sustainability, providing students with the tools to design a case study by: describing the scope of sustainable development, listing the questions to be asked, and developing a prioritization strategy to solve the identified problem.

In addition, emphasis will be placed on Kirkpatrick's training evaluation model: Reaction (Did trainees enjoy the training?), Learning (Was there a transfer of learning?), Impact (Did the training change behaviour?), Results (Did the training affect performance). How assessment makes students compete with each other.

The lecture will continue with a focus on sustainability as a result of users' active participation in the innovation process within LL. To complete the course, students will be asked to conduct a realistic evaluation.

5 Next methodological steps

This deliverable reports the methodology and implementation towards the creation of a postgraduate course that was done until M18 of the VITALISE project. However, the creation of the master course is a demanding procedure that will go beyond the VITALISE project duration. VITALISE objective and expected outcomes is to design the material and timeline for a course and pilot it in a smaller scale. The first steps towards this objective have been implemented and reported in the current document.

From this point on, the work will continue with the finalization of the **phase three** of the Dynamic Curriculum model. A first part of this phase has already been implemented with the creation of the lesson's summaries. This will continue with the analysis of the existing summaries in order to identify possible repetitions or overlapping. The summaries will be structured based on the 5E model that will enhance the provision of a coherent instruction to the learner. The partners will work together to identify and analyse any cultural differences that exist in the various consortium countries and identify the particularities of each teaching approach. After the finalization of the summaries, the partners will work on the creation of the course material and tools to be offered.

Although VITALISE is designing a complete master course, it is not considered feasible to implement the whole program based on time and resources constraints. During the **phase four** of the Dynamic Curriculum model, we will work on implements a subset of the designed lessons that can be piloted in a semester course. This will be offered jointly in 4 VITALISE universities (AUTH, McGill, UPM, LAUREA) in parallel with the ongoing curriculum courses. This piloting phase will help identify any methodological issues that have not been identified during the design. It will also start some discussions on the regulatory aspects of providing a joint cross-national master course.

The last phase, phase five, that will run in parallel with phase four is the assessment and evaluation of the course. This will be done on two fronts, from the students' perspective and from the teachers/professor's perspective. It is important to understand what the acquired skills for the students are, what they think about the lessons offered, how important do teachers perceive their contributions. Another important point is how important are the skills offered to students for the market. All these will be assessed following a multi method approach that will include questionnaires, interviews and quantitative measures of attendance, job upgrades after course completion etc.

The outcome of VITALISE is envisaged to be an exploitable multi-national postgraduate course. More specifically, VITALISE will conclude with the provision of material, timeline and results of piloting assessment that will lead to further improvement of the course in order to be ready for full implementation.

6 Conclusions

This document presented the methodology and first draft summaries of the lessons that will consist of the VITALISE postgraduate course. This master course entitled “MSc in Innovation through Living Labs and Entrepreneurship” is designed following two parallel methodological approaches: the Dynamic Curriculum model for designing the curriculum and the 5E model for designing the lesson of the master course. Although a first outline of the master course and summaries for the lessons already exist, there is still work to be done on analyzing and structuring the summaries, preparing the material and finally organizing the piloting activities. The conclusive activity for VITALISE task will be the evaluation of the pilot in order to produce improvement guidelines. The course along with the improvement guidelines will be an exploitable outcome for VITALISE that we envision to be sustainable after the end of the project.

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D4.7 University Course design

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Appendices

Appendix 1

MSc in Innovation through Living Labs and Entrepreneurship						
Course modules	Course module name	Key skills to be learn	Lecture 1	Lecture 2	Lecture 3	Lecture 4
1	Course introduction and orientation	Understanding the course objectives and committing to forthcoming studying tasks	Introduction of course objectives and learning outcomes Introduction of course participants via icebreaker exercise Introduction of SE Method of Instruction Transdisciplinary communication and understanding AUTH	Holistic view and specific knowledge on sustainability Use of virtual learning environments and resources LAUREA	Understand platform interaction and expectations Networking with participants and experts AUTH	
2	Theoretical foundation of user centric methods and innovation	Understanding the theoretical foundations and becoming familiar with the current body of knowledge regarding user centric innovation	What is a living lab? Living lab as research Infrastructure Types of LL environments: Research LLs, Corporate LLs, Organizational LLs, Intermediary LLs, A time limited LLs. 6 How LLs can become part of a transformative institutional change that draws on both top-down and bottom-up strategies in the pursuit of sustainability Living Lab Key Principles: value, influence, sustainability, openness, realism,..... ENOLL	User-centric design / Design thinking. The meaning to know what the user actually wants and needs. Basic concepts theories and terminology id call this element: key concepts and terminologies in KT Knowledge translation: How is it done? What are the gaps, what causes them and what are interventions. Implementation science (Separating KT from IS) Methods and theories to do KT/KM UPM	Agile development Learn how established LLs can adopt this approach to renew their surveys, look into problems from a different angle and redesign internal processes Public- Private Partnership (PPP), LLs as "functional regions" enabling actors have settled down PPP of companies, public entities, universities, institutes and individuals. Innovation ecosystem, co-creation A learning loop in a complex community like LL, includes Social learning - networks and forums for deliberation and exchange AUTH	Introduction of the "family" of different user centric research methods and processes (list what are covered) Research and Development (R&D) process; in-situ methods to capture the temporal and contextual nuances of users' practices; Benefits and challenges of user centric research and innovation innovation as a process of turning opportunity into new ideas and of putting these into wide used practice AIT
3	Innovation typology	Understanding different innovation types and their relation to user centric innovation methods	Open vs closed innovation vs idea Sustainable innovation Social innovation Inclusivity and sustainability placing citizens at the heart of the innovation process GAIA Radical/disruptive vs. incremental innovation AV	Business model innovation Data driven innovation Technology driven innovation Innovation as a key driver for economic and social growth AV		
4	Stakeholder identification	Understanding and classification from the perspective of the different user types and the different contexts they operate in	Degrees of user involvement and discussion from the perspective of the different user-centric designs 3-4-5 helix theory ENOLL	Open innovation ecosystems Multi-stakeholder approach orchestration LLs interactions Other LL Funding organisations Clusters, Government RTOs, Large Companies SMEs, Investors, Business Organisations, Education & Training, Policy Makers GAIA	Techniques and methods for stakeholder analysis, mapping and identification. Stakeholder mapping and analysis ENOLL	
5	Needs assessment and problem definition	Ability to identify user needs, scope the problem and find the opportunity for innovation You may need to understand more about the problem you're trying to solve	What is needs assessment / analysis? The focus is to encourage users to express their thoughts and attitudes towards the concepts being developed from the basis of their needs What is the (real) problem? Explain the importance of problem framing How can we co-design solutions to our community's problems? How can we advocate for individual or community needs? SIT	Techniques for need assessment (Observation, survey, desktop research, interviews etc.) Need data analysis techniques Problem scoping Foresighting (future needs, trends, ...) AIT Use cases. Learn how established LLs can adopt the problem solving approach to renew their surveys, look into problems from a different angle and redesign internal processes. LICALAB		
6	Survey, interview and focus group methodologies in user centric research	Ability to execute survey, interview and focus group methods	Typology of research methods: Qualitative & quantitative & mixed methods Background research. The purpose of background research is to align what we want to make with what users want to use. Desktop research and state of the art Quantitative methods Validated survey instruments in user centric research How to design and the guidelines rules of engagement Key principles SIT	Qualitative Individual interview techniques in user centric research TREBAG Focus group interview techniques in user centric research Online survey tools Crowdsourcing as the collection of information, opinions, or work from a group of people, usually sourced via the internet.TREBAG		
7	Co-creation sessions Ideation, conceptualization and prototyping techniques	Ability to understand and use co-creation techniques for ideating, concept creation and prototyping. Recognise the potential of co-creation	Understanding similarities and differences between idea, concept and prototype TREBAG Implementation science (Separating KT from IS) Methods and theories to do KT/KM McGill	Workshop planning and timing (dos and don'ts) Workshop facilitation techniques. The co-creation workshops are seen as a central aspect of the LL network as they bring together researchers and stakeholders into the prototyping space. Ice breaker techniques, TREBAG Co-creation techniques for ideation and conceptualization in workshop settings (selection of templates) Techniques to conceptualize and prototype (e.g. Sketching, wizard-of-oz, virtual, role playing, storyboard, paper prototype) LICALAB	Tools to run online workshop (e.g. Miro,) virtual spaces TREBAG Techniques to ideate Creativity boosting techniques TREBAG Design sprint and open innovation camp & hacatons LAUREA	
8	Testing experimentation and validation techniques	Understanding different types of testing methods. Ability to formulate testing plan and conduct testing for different types of test	Typology of testing - idea, concept, feasibility, prototype, usability, real life testing SIT Testing and intervention planning, resources and management timing (dos and don'ts) CERTH	Online and Offline testing methods: Idea testing, concept testing, prototype testing, feasibility/usability testing, real-life testing, proof-of-concept. (tools, methods such as mockups), CERTH Testbeds, Research Infrastructures, Technology Infrastructures UPM		
9	Research ethics and legal issues Data management and protection	Ability to execute living lab research in ethical way and follow GDPR requirements Ability to create data management plan and foster open data principles	Basic ethics concepts Dimensions of Ethics (Normative Ethics, Descriptive Ethics (Comparative Ethics), Applied Ethics GDPR issues Informed consent (legal requirements and examples for different contextual settings) The confidentiality of user's data INTRAS	IPR and copyright in open innovation projects Intellectual property arising from the research collaboration TREBAG Publications and transfers or research results LLSA Ethical application and ethical committees. MDR (medical device regulation) LLSA	Open and FAIR data principles Responsible Research and Innovation Data management planning Data protection Data anonymization Identify data sources LAUREA	Collaborative Research Agreement Process (Learn how the agreement describes the actions that each organization has agreed to undertake, and defines the obligations each party has to the others participating in the collaborative research effort) Compliance with export control and other laws and regulations Rights and procedures to terminate the project LLSA
10	User / research panel management	Theoretical foundations of user/research panel management	Ability recruit and manage user panels User panel management (online vs. offline) Recruiting and maintaining strategies (do and don't) Sample selection including inclusion and exclusion strategies. Utilization of commercial market research panels LICALAB	Unlimited and extended profiling can be done by having panel members sign up and take surveys for profiling Option to communicate with members via email LAUREA	Export/import panelist data Search/filter panel members. VITALISE TOOL Panel update, motivations and dropout strategies Roadmapping for panel engagement LAUREA	
11	Living lab project planning and management	Ability define project plan for a living lab project	Research design for own "user centric project" Intervention planning via template McGill	Refer to the Innovation projects and activities carried out within a living lab GAIA Work on your own entrepreneurial or research project, gaining hands-on experience in transforming an idea into a sustainable business model TREBAG		
12	Entrepreneurship	Collaborate effectively with your team in LLs and generate ideas that drive innovation and entrepreneurship	Transforming an idea into a sustainable business model with a measurable positive impact on society and the environment (Business Plan) (Business case examples) AV	How LL services can accelerate access to the market VIL		
13	Sustainability	How the co-creation of knowledge and practices takes place within LLs to address sustainability challenges	LL labelling framework (ENOLL evaluation ISPM paper) Learn the way in which LLs contribute to sustainability transitions (SDGs Sustainable Development Goals) ENOLL	Sustainability and scalability of LL GAIA Living Lab Business Model (canvas, PROVA health etc) and LL Business Plan VIL	Methods and examples on how an LL can be open to innovation coming from its ecosystem. (It relates to the governance of the living labs and how easily any stakeholder can go through your LL for their innovation. UPM	Evaluation and sustainability - Realistic Evaluation AUTH